

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Recommendations for a federated system of taxonomically curated reference libraries

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Executive summary

Species identification from environmental DNA (eDNA) sequencing critically depends on the availability and quality of reference sequences to which to compare the obtained environmental sequences. For eDNA-based taxonomic identification to be routinely implemented in aquatic monitoring programs, these taxonomic assignments should be undertaken with quality-controlled and taxonomically curated reference libraries to minimise false or incomplete assignments. These reference libraries should additionally be easy to find and reuse. The current eDNAqua-Plan deliverable report D3.1 outlines the vision of a federated system of taxonomically curated reference libraries, and a set of guiding principles towards achieving this vision. The guidelines contain recommendations of essential metadata that reference libraries should provide, which cover the biological origin, sequence information and taxonomy and taxonomic validation of reference sequences as well as overall library metadata. Subsequently, the report outlines recommended curation procedures focused on sequence quality, taxonomic curation and a ranking of the reference quality. Finally, a proposal of interoperable metadata fields using existing standards and avenues for a decentralised data architecture paves the way towards an interoperable, federated network. These three pillars of essential metadata, curation procedures and interoperability are established to support the eDNAqua-Plan vision of a federated network of curated reference libraries to support reproducible and reliable molecular aquatic biodiversity monitoring in Europe and beyond.

Figure 1. Summary of the three pillars needed to improve curated reference libraries for Europe.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
BINS	Barcode Index Number System
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
BOLD	The Barcode of Life Data Systems
DDBJ	DNA Data Bank of Japan
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DwC	Darwin Core
EC	European Commission
ECB	European Central Bank
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GSC	Global Standards Consortium
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (NCBI, ENA, DDBJ)
MiXS	Minimum Information of any (x) Sequence
MOTU	Molecular Operational Taxonomic Unit
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
SU	Sorbonne Université
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards (originally Taxonomic Databases Working Group)
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package(s)

1. Introduction

Climate changes and human actions continue to impact Europe’s aquatic environment and biodiversity. Sequencing technologies are rapidly evolving, with cost per sequenced base continuing to reduce and compact sequencers that can be used in the field becoming available, facilitating the mass production of eDNA-derived data for biodiversity monitoring. Computing and data infrastructures are also changing at pace. The mainstream adoption of FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and the advent of technologies such as semantic web, Resource Description Framework (RDF), and Linked Open Data, provide increased community drive and potential solutions to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data. Increased data interoperability for machines has downstream benefits in the data processing ecosystem, including for example the potential to incorporate AI into analytical pipelines.

In the rapidly evolving environmental DNA (eDNA) field, the international scientific and political context offers many opportunities, but also significant challenges, including limited government budgets and balancing of national vs. international priorities. This makes the value of efforts to map the current eDNA landscape and propose pragmatic solutions important and urgent.

WP3 of the eDNAqua-Plan project aims to map the current eDNA and reference library data landscape. Analysis from WP2 identified significant gaps and highlighted two major categories for aquatic eDNA analysis that have different data flows: (1) regular biomonitoring by governmental agencies, and (2) academic research. WP4 implemented a variety of practical use cases for aquatic eDNA analysis. WP3 ran a workshop (milestone 5, M3.1) in September 2024 focused on standards of the current eDNA and reference library data ecosystem and explored the related processes and stakeholders of the ecosystem. Task T3.3 has additionally researched how biobanks fit into this ecosystem and is currently mapping how different biodiversity repositories link to each other. A second WP3 workshop (milestone 6, M3.2) in January 2025 focussed on brainstorming the future landscape. Milestone 7 M3.3 in April 2024 was a result of these joint efforts and describes the first version of a recommended future digital ecosystem. This D3.1 deliverable is a report of proposed best practices for reference libraries including a set of machine-interpretable criteria to evaluate reliable references.

Table 1. Reference library relevant definitions

Term	Definition
Interoperable	The ability of different databases, systems, and tools to exchange, interpret, and use data consistently and accurately across platforms without loss of meaning or functionality.
Machine readable	The capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with no (or minimal) human intervention
Metadata	The information associated with each DNA sequence record and workflows that provide biological, technical, and contextual details necessary for correct interpretation, validation, and reuse of the data.
Metadata checklist	Typically a table of the mandatory, recommended and optional metadata for reference libraries
Metadata standard	A (meta)data “standard” means any type of agreed upon set of formats, schemas, vocabularies and methods for sharing/exposing data to ensure findability and accessibility. Ideally these are defined by an international standards body.
Reference library	A digital library with DNA sequence data and associated metadata that can be used as a reference to assign sequences of unknown origin to a taxon (e.g. species, genus...).

The importance of reliable, taxonomically curated reference libraries

Environmental DNA sequencing has revolutionized biodiversity assessment by enabling the detection of organisms from trace genetic material in environmental samples. However, **the power of eDNA sequencing approaches depends critically on the quality and completeness of reference sequence libraries used for taxonomic assignment** (Box 1). Inaccurate, incomplete, or inconsistently curated databases can lead to misidentifications, false positives, and significant underestimation of diversity, especially for poorly characterized microbial and protistan lineages. **Reliable, taxonomically curated reference libraries provide the foundation for accurate taxonomic identification, ecological inference, and biogeographical comparison.** They ensure reproducibility and cross-study comparability, allowing eDNA data to be meaningfully integrated into ecological networks, global monitoring programs, and evolutionary analyses. Expanding and curating these libraries according to commonly applied standards is therefore essential for translating raw sequence data into robust biological knowledge.

Box 1. What is a “DNA sequence reference library”?

A DNA sequence reference library is defined here as a digital library with DNA sequence data and associated metadata that can be used as a reference to assign sequences of unknown origin to a taxon (e.g. species, genus, family ...).

Current reference libraries have varying standards and levels of implementation of curation and annotation procedures. Some of them are focused on a particular group of organisms and integrate thorough curation procedures (e.g. Diat.barcode, PR2, UNITE). Usually these are libraries supported by a community of deeply engaged experts that ensure high quality standards and reliability. Other reference libraries consist of major data repositories with very broad scope (e.g. INSDC, BOLD), that aggregate DNA sequence data from diverse taxa and sources. In this case, records tend to have disparate levels of quality and curation, even within the same repository. For example, records must adhere to minimum standards to be deposited in BOLD, with those that meet a stricter set of standards receiving a “barcode compliance” annotation (Ratnasingham et al., 2024). However, in the case of BOLD records mined from GenBank, these standards do not apply.

Hence, depending on the target communities, researchers may be able to use databases with thoroughly curated records (e.g. diatoms), or may need to resort to large broad-scope repositories (e.g. macroinvertebrates) that integrate records with uneven internal standards. Uncritical usage of large DNA sequence repositories may lead to erroneous taxonomic assignments, particularly when employing unsupervised taxonomic assignments to millions of reads typically generated by high-throughput sequencing (HTS) approaches.

To overcome these limitations, efforts have been made to create curated reference libraries by extracting and curating subsets of data from major repositories (e.g. Midori, Silva, MetaZooGene, European NIS; Lavrador et al. 2023), but several shortcomings remain. Firstly, there is no general agreement on curation procedures, meaning the extent and quality of curation varies. In fact, few databases carry out full curation down to expert verification of the validity of the association of a species name with a reference sequence. Secondly, individual species-by-species curation procedures are impractical for large groups of organisms due to the huge number of species involved and lack of manpower (e.g. marine invertebrates, Radulovici et al. 2021). Thirdly, the few automated curation procedures available (e.g. BAGS, Fontes et al. 2021) have their own technical limitations, currently preventing complete and sound curation.

The eDNAqua-Plan proposal for a federated system of reference libraries

The idea of creating a single, centralized, fully-curated reference library is appealing, but this potential solution is widely considered to be impractical for many reasons, not the least of which would be the difficulty of obtaining centralized long-term funding and the breadth of taxonomic expertise that would be required. **The ideal realistic future landscape thus consists of independently curated and maintained reference libraries which follow common guiding principles, are interconnected, and searchable through a common metadata portal (Figure 2).** Reference libraries would ideally adhere to common principles of metadata publishing, quality control, and taxonomic curation, ensuring transparency and traceability. **Libraries that meet these standards should be federated within a common network, enabling information exchange, interoperability, and findability, and ultimately ensuring their reuse across eDNA projects.** Keeping libraries independent will maintain the commitment of taxonomy experts to their libraries, which might not be the case for a large generalist database. Furthermore, keeping libraries independent but interconnected will bring flexibility and sustainability to the system, both for library users (who will be able to choose the library best suited to their study) and for the experts who maintain them. Finally, this coordinated framework would greatly improve the reliability and comparability of eDNA-based biodiversity assessments.

The current report sets out the vision for this future landscape and proposes the concrete principles to which reliable reference libraries should adhere. This proposal builds on a landscape analysis of reference libraries conducted by eDNAquaPlan in WP2 (Costa et al. 2025), as well as the cumulative expertise of multiple libraries and data users, which are either part of the eDNAqua-Plan consortium or were consulted through workshops and other channels. These are detailed in the [methodology](#), followed by the [proposed set of essential metadata](#), [quality and taxonomic curation principles](#), and finally a set of [guiding principles to establish the network of interoperable libraries](#). Finally, this report proposes to establish these principles as a new standard for reference libraries.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the eDNAqua-Plan vision for a federated system of curated reference libraries. DB1, DB2 ... represent independent reference libraries following common principles that enable them to be searchable through a common data portal.

2. Methodology

Workshops and stakeholder consultations

The recommendations constituting this report were shaped by the different internal workshops and external stakeholder consultations that were organised or attended within the eDNAqua-Plan project and consortium. A first in-person, internal workshop was held on September 13th, 2024 following the General Assembly in Spala, Poland to discuss standards requirements. It was preceded by a seminar on the curation of reference databases, followed by two sessions of parallel group discussions covering three topics related to reference databases: 1) the storage of vouchers, DNA-material and DNA-barcodes, data and associated metadata, 2) taxonomic curation procedures, and 3) machine-readable workflows and data standards for interconnectable libraries. The outcomes of these discussions laid the groundwork of our recommendations for curation principles and essential metadata, and can be consulted in the Milestone 5 workshop proceedings (Babo et al. 2024). The following year, another internal workshop was held online on February 28th, 2025, for conceptualising and documenting the eDNA data ecosystem. During this workshop, consortium members and invited stakeholders evaluated the current eDNA data ecosystem in Europe at different levels, including reference libraries, considering the different databases and repositories, data flows between them, metadata requirements, standards and taxonomies used. This evaluation served as a basis to envision the ideal future of this (European) eDNA data landscape, as well as changes needed to achieve that future. The discussions defined the eDNAqua-Plan vision for a federated network of reference libraries, and the outcomes can be consulted in the Milestone 6 workshop proceedings (Boulanger et al. 2025) and subsequent Milestone 7 conceptual landscape proposal (Boulanger et al. 2025).

The vision and concrete recommendations were further developed throughout the project and presented in multiple conferences or workshops where the input from audience members or workshop participants helped shape this work. Finally, these recommendations have already been included in external stakeholder consultation processes led by WP5 which will refine the eDNAqua-Plan Blueprint, through the Blueprint workshop held online on the 8th and 9th of October 2025 including 65 external stakeholders, and Roadmap, through the Roadmap survey launched on the 19th of December 2025 targeting 300+ stakeholders (closing date February 19th, 2026).

3. Proposal for a set of essential metadata

A reference barcode must be accompanied by a minimum set of metadata to ensure its reliability. Here, the DNA sequence is considered as primary data and all accompanying information as metadata. Having the appropriate metadata accompanying a reference sequence allows verification of the identification of the sequence, which is crucial to curate taxonomic assignments and ensure the quality/reliability of downstream results.

A set of essential metadata

Several recommendations already exist to describe the metadata accompanying sequence information, particularly reference barcodes. Previous reference library recommendations (e.g. BOLD - Ratnasingham et al. 2024, EU Cost DNAquaNet network - Rimet et al. 2021, European Committee for Standardisation - CEN 2014) advocate comprehensive metadata requirements that include detailed information on sampling methods, geographic location, voucher material, DNA extraction protocols, and sequencing procedures. While such information is essential for evaluating the technical validity of barcode records, it is not strictly necessary for most end-users interpreting eDNA datasets. Many of these users do not possess advanced taxonomic expertise and primarily require confidence in the accuracy of species assignments rather than access to methodological details. **We therefore recommend that the critical assessment and validation of barcode quality should be a mandatory responsibility of the reference library itself, rather than being delegated to end-users.** Using the unique source sample identifier and/or sequence accession number (mandatory fields for reference libraries), reference library experts responsible for this assessment should be able to find this information in the databases of the institutes hosting specimens and/or in linked publications. In an ideal future landscape, this should be possible in an automated manner if resources are sufficiently interoperable. Our recommendation for the minimum set of essential metadata for reference libraries therefore focuses on a **relatively restricted set of fields** that allow end-users to: **(1) easily identify whether the taxonomic assignment linked to a barcode is trustworthy**, and **(2) be able to filter database entries according to a set of pertinent criteria (geographic location, habitat type, environmental parameters, etc.)**.

In this context, we recommend that each barcode record should at minimum include a limited set of standardized, traceable, and verifiable metadata describing the **biological origin, sequence quality**, and **taxonomic validation** of the reference. Based on the overview of existing standards and relevant literature, we propose the following set of metadata that is **considered mandatory for reference libraries** (note that this list in no way precludes inclusion of any additional metadata in reference library records, Table 2).

Table 2: Recommended minimum mandatory metadata requirements for aquatic DNA reference libraries

Metadata Type	Entity	Description	Example
Biological Origin	Source sample identifier	Unique specimen code, voucher number, or strain code.	RCC1502
	Repository	Name of the museum, biobank, culture collection from which the specimen originates.	VLIZ
	Sample type	Indicates whether the barcode originates from an individual specimen, a culture, or an environmental sequencing dataset.	Culture
	Voucher type	Specimen, tissue, DNA extract, image, etc	Tissue
	Date of collection	Date of original collection of sample, preferably in ISO format (YYY-MM-DD).	1998-04-06
	Geographical coordinates	Latitude/longitude (expressed in decimal values in WGS84 format or in a different, specified geographical position system).	+48.1697 -1.2261
	Country	Country (including Exclusive Economic Zone) of origin of source sample ("international waters" if beyond national jurisdiction).	France
	Source sample identification	Taxonomic name linked to source specimen by the person who originally identified it (for specimens / cultures)	Heterosigma akashiwo
	Original identification method	Morphological, molecular, or both.	Morphological
	Type material	Is the specimen or culture used to generate the barcode the same specimen or culture designated as type material (or isotype, holotype ...) of the taxon.	Type material
	Project link	PID (DOI) or URI Link to either the original paper describing the voucher, or link to a database containing the metadata of the voucher, including images.	doi...
Sequence Quality	Sequence accession number	Accession number assigned by sequence repository.	LC214052.1
	Source database name	Database hosting the sequence (ENA, GenBank, BOLD, PR2, etc.).	GenBank
	Source database version	Version or release of the database where the sequence is deposited.	269.0
	Marker / gene region	Genetic marker sequenced (e.g., 18S, COI, rbcL, ITS).	18S rDNA
	Sequencing platform	Sequencing platform (e.g. Sanger, Illumina, Nanopore, Aviti ...)	Illumina
	Sequencing instrument	Sequencing instrument	HI-SEQ
	Quality metrics	Quality indicators (e.g. % ambiguous bases, Phred score).	0% ambiguous bases
	Quality control notes	Quality control notes (e.g., chimera check, contamination screening, trimming notes)	Still has adapters present
Taxonomy & Taxonomic Validation	Curation status	Data status (raw, expert-reviewed).	Expert reviewed
	Curator / validator	Expert reviewer name (and optional institution/contact).	I. Probert
	Date of expert validation (optional)	Date when curation was performed.	2026-02-23
	Curation method (optional)	Method used (phylogeny, clustering, etc.).	Phylogeny
	Confidence level score	Assigned confidence score or rank (note that libraries should clearly explain how confidence levels are assessed - see Section 4.4).	4

Metadata Type	Entity	Description	Example
	Scientific name	Current valid scientific name (most reliable identification to lowest possible taxonomic rank).	Heterosigma akashiwo
	Taxonomic identifier	Identifier corresponding to the scientific name (e.g., NCBI TaxID, WoRMS AlphaID).	160585
	Taxonomic source	Source taxonomy (WoRMS, AlgaeBase, NCBI Taxonomy, SILVA, ...).	WoRMS
	Taxonomic rank	Lowest rank assigned (species, genus, family, etc.).	Species
Library Metadata	Library name	Name of the barcode/reference library.	PR2
	Library version number	Version identifier of the library.	5.1.1
	Library version date	Date associated with the library version.	2025-10-27
	Library marker region coverage	List of marker genes that this reference library covers. (Ideally, these are controlled vocabulary)	mtDNA 12S
	Library geographic coverage	The continent, countries or seas which this library is focused on.	Belgian North Sea
	Library taxonomic coverage	The main taxonomic groups targeted in this reference library.	Eukaryotes
	Library taxonomic system	The taxonomic backbone used in this reference library.	WoRMS
	Library publication	A (or several) paper(s) describing the library	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gks1160
	Library link	A URL hyperlink to the reference library.	https://pr2-database.org
	Library total records	The total number of records present in this library.	220,000

Most existing reference libraries already include all —or the majority— of these fields. However, the terminology used to describe equivalent entities varies substantially among libraries. To ensure effective interoperability within the proposed federated system, terminology should be harmonised according to recognised standards, or at the very least cross-mapped (see Section 5.1). Without such harmonisation, semantic inconsistencies will continue to hinder data integration, automated exchange, and cross-platform analyses.

We note that, under current Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) frameworks implementing the Nagoya Protocol to the Convention on Biological Diversity, obligations relating to sampling permits —such as Prior Informed Consent (PIC), Mutually Agreed Terms (MAT), and/or an Internationally Recognized Certificate of Compliance (IRCC)— generally apply to the original access to physical genetic resources. The downstream use of publicly available sequence data, in the absence of new physical access to genetic resources from a provider country, does not typically trigger independent ABS permitting requirements. However, the regulatory landscape is evolving in light of ongoing international negotiations concerning Digital Sequence Information (DSI). Should new multilateral benefit-sharing mechanisms or national implementing measures introduce additional compliance obligations for DSI use, it may become necessary to incorporate information related to access permits into the minimum metadata requirements for reference libraries.

4. Curation procedures

4.1 Framework

Curation procedures comprise three complementary components, all of which are necessary to ensure the overall quality and reliability of the reference library (Figure 3). Firstly, sequence quality must be verified (Section 4.2). Secondly, taxonomic names must be harmonised within a given phylogenetic clade, or among identical or near-identical sequences, to ensure consistency, a process that can be assisted by automated pipelines (Section 4.3). Thirdly, taxonomic assignments must be evaluated and assigned a quality ranking to reflect the level of confidence and reliability (Section 4.4). Below we present recommendations for these curation procedures.

Figure 3. Curation procedures workflow. There are three steps necessary to make library taxonomic assignments reliable.

4.2 Sequence quality curation

This initial step does not constitute taxonomic curation per se, but is a prerequisite for ensuring sequence integrity and technical reliability (e.g., Pentinsaari et al., 2020). Its objective is to detect sequencing artefacts, amplification errors, and structural inconsistencies prior to any taxonomic assessment.

Several types of verification should be undertaken. Basic quality control includes evaluation of the proportion of undetermined nucleotides (e.g. “N”), detection of unexpected homopolymers, identification of reverse-complement artefacts, and screening for insertions or deletions (indels). In protein-coding markers, indels should not be present unless biologically justified, as they disrupt the reading frame. Multiple sequence alignments are particularly useful for identifying frameshifts, premature stop codons, and anomalous divergence patterns relative to closely related sequences.

For ribosomal markers such as SSU and LSU, additional structural validation is recommended. Hidden Markov Model (HMM) profile matching can be used to confirm correct gene identity and boundary detection. Secondary structure consistency should also be assessed, as rRNA genes exhibit conserved structural motifs. Tools such as Ribovore (Schäffer et al., 2021) enable automated validation of rRNA sequences and facilitate the generation of high-quality SSU and LSU datasets suitable for inclusion in curated resources such as RefSeq.

An acceptable level of sequence quality should be defined using transparent, reproducible, and marker-specific criteria. These criteria should be established a priori and consistently applied across the reference library. Recommended thresholds may include:

- **Ambiguous bases (“N”):** Below a defined percentage (e.g., <1% of sequence length, or zero for short barcode regions).

- **Sequence length:** Within an expected size range for the target marker (e.g., $\pm 5\text{--}10\%$ of the canonical barcode length).
- **Reading frame integrity (coding genes):** No internal stop codons; no frameshifts unless biologically supported.
- **Indels (coding regions):** Absent or biologically justified and consistent across related sequences.
- **Alignment coherence:** No extreme divergence relative to phylogenetically close sequences unless independently verified.
- **Marker confirmation (rRNA genes):** Positive HMM profile match and structurally plausible secondary structure.
- **Contamination screening:** No unexpected high-similarity matches to unrelated taxa (e.g., via BLAST screening).

Quality thresholds may be tiered (e.g., high-quality, acceptable, low-confidence) rather than binary, allowing sequences that marginally fail certain criteria to be retained but flagged accordingly. Importantly, acceptance criteria should reflect the intended downstream use of the reference library (e.g., regulatory biomonitoring may require stricter thresholds than exploratory biodiversity surveys). By formalising explicit quality metrics and documenting applied thresholds, reference libraries can ensure transparency, reproducibility, and consistent sequence reliability prior to taxonomic curation.

4.3 Taxonomic curation

Taxonomic curation is an essential step in the construction of a reference library. When taxonomic names are inconsistent within a given clade—or among genetically identical or highly similar sequences—downstream metabarcoding analyses are directly affected. Inconsistent nomenclature can lead to divergent outcomes depending on the assignment algorithm used. For example, naïve Bayesian classifiers such as RDP may fail to assign a taxonomic name when reference labels are conflicting, whereas similarity-based approaches such as BLAST may return heterogeneous or equally plausible names. Such discrepancies complicate interpretation and can substantially hinder downstream ecological or biomonitoring analyses. To ensure reliable and interpretable outputs, **a formal taxonomic curation procedure is therefore required to harmonise the taxonomic annotations of sequences within the reference library.**

Heterogeneity in taxonomic naming may arise from several sources (Rimet et al., 2019). First, multiple taxonomic reference systems coexist, and taxonomy itself evolves over time as classifications are revised. As a result, synonymous names, outdated nomenclature, and alternative classifications may be present within a single database. Second, the taxonomic expertise of sequence submitters varies considerably, and different conceptual frameworks (e.g., biological, morphological, or genetic species concepts) may be applied when delimiting taxa. Third, low-quality or erroneous sequences may lead to incorrect identifications and propagate misannotations. Effective taxonomic curation must address each of these issues to ensure internal consistency and reliability.

Following sequence quality control (Section 4.2), one or more dedicated tools and procedures can be employed to harmonise and validate taxonomic names across the reference library: phylogenies (§4.3.1), molecular clustering (§4.3.2), automated curation procedures (§4.3.3).

4.3.1. Expert curation based on phylogenies

The objective of this procedure is to reconstruct a phylogeny that enables the evaluation and harmonisation of taxonomic annotations within the reference library. Phylogenetic reconstruction provides an explicit evolutionary framework in which inconsistencies in taxonomic naming can be detected. The choice of algorithm depends largely on dataset size and available computational resources. For large datasets, approximate maximum-likelihood approaches such as FastTree may be preferred due to their computational efficiency, whereas more computationally intensive methods such as RAxML may provide increased accuracy for moderate-sized datasets.

Once the phylogenetic tree has been inferred, an expert evaluates the consistency of taxonomic names within well-supported clades. Sequences that cluster together with strong statistical support are expected to bear homogeneous taxonomic annotations. When inconsistencies are detected among phylogenetically neighbouring sequences, further verification is required.

Several steps may be undertaken to resolve such discrepancies:

1. **Consultation of peer-reviewed literature:** If sequences are associated with published studies, the taxonomic conclusions of those publications should be examined and, where appropriate, used to correct or update sequence annotations.
2. **Verification of nomenclatural status and synonyms:** In the absence of supporting publications, the names assigned to sequences should be checked for synonyms or outdated nomenclature using authoritative taxonomic databases such as AlgaeBase, DiatomBase, or World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS). This step helps reconcile alternative names referring to the same taxon and align annotations with current taxonomic standards.
3. **Evaluation of available metadata:** If inconsistencies persist, associated metadata—such as specimen images, geographic origin, habitat information, or voucher material—should be examined to refine identifications and achieve taxonomic coherence within the clade.

Phylogenetic reconstruction is widely used to support expert-driven taxonomic curation in several established reference libraries, including EukRef, EukRef-Ciliophora, Diat.barcode, and PhyMyco-DB.

4.3.2. Expert curation based on clustering genetically similar sequences

In this procedure, sequences are clustered based on their genetic similarity. Experts can then check the homogeneity of the taxonomic names given to sequences in each cluster, as in 4.3.1. The way these clusters are named can vary: OTU (operational taxonomical unit), MOTU (molecular operational taxonomical unit), BINS (Barcode Index Number System, Ratnasingham et al. 2013).

BOLD database's community uses this procedure to help experts to curate its library using visual outputs. R packages like BAGS can be used to help expert auditing and curating sequences: it gives to each species of the reference library a ranking quality score (from consolidated to discordant species assignment), according to the attributes of the data and congruence of species names with sequences clustered in barcode index numbers (BINS).

After running the cluster analysis, the expert can follow the verifications (points 1, 2, 3) given in 4.3.1. to curate the taxonomic names.

4.3.3. Expert curation based on self assignment

In this procedure, the reference library is assigned on itself to check for incongruities between expected and obtained taxonomic assignments. Self-assignment can be undertaken with algorithms like RDP or BLAST. The reference library EukRibo uses this procedure, as well as the adapted Diat.barcode (e.g. Rimet 2024) library for metabarcoding pipelines (<https://carrtel-collection.hub.inrae.fr/barcoding-databases/diat.barcode/pipelines-and-aligned-and-trimed-database>).

After running the self-assignment, the expert can follow the verifications (points 1, 2, 3) given in 4.3.1. to curate taxonomic names.

4.3.4 Automated curation procedures based on bioinformatics or AI

Automated bioinformatics-based curation systems are urgently needed to handle the massive amounts and the complexity of reference library data, particularly for large-scale libraries of broad taxonomic scope. In such cases, the human-based revision and annotation may require too much effort and time to be feasible (e.g. Radulovici et al., 2021).

Automation may be full, i.e. all records in a given database, or partial. In the latter case, the goal is to have most of the records revised and annotated bioinformatically, leaving only a minority of the records for human (expert)-based revision.

In the short term it is expected that most curation systems will be semi-automated, progressively tending to full automation as AI systems develop further and become more accurate. Nevertheless, human-intervention may always be required, even if at a minor scale, particularly for clarifying intricacies at low taxonomic levels (i.e. species).

Indeed, whereas some components of curation, such as specimens and sequence metadata completeness and validity appear to be at reach of automation (with varying levels of difficulty depending on each case), the true challenge is to automate the revision of the accuracy of the taxonomic assignments at species level.

Curation systems implemented in reference libraries of aquatic organisms vary considerably in the extent and type of curation approach (Costa et al. 2025). Diat.barcode (Rimet et al. 2019) and UNITE (Abarenkov et al. 2023.) are examples of well-established semi-automated systems that require human intervention for ambiguous records only at fine taxonomic levels (e.g. species or species hypothesis respectively). Although these systems are tailored to particular groups of organisms, namely diatoms and fungi, respectively, their approach may inspire the development of more complete and accurate curation systems for other groups of organisms. Automated curation systems should strive for the following:

- Complete curation of all records down to species-level with minimization of human intervention;
- Broad application to the largest possible taxonomic scope;
- Detailed and accessible criteria and procedures for curation;
- Traceable and annotated curation actions;
- Implementation as Open Source to enable auditing and refinement;

4.4 Quality ranking system of sequence taxonomy

Many curated reference libraries implement a ranking system that assigns a quality score or confidence level to taxonomic annotations. These systems aim to provide transparency regarding the reliability of each taxonomic assignment and to guide downstream users in interpreting results. For example:

- UNITE assigns “Taxonomic Hypothesis” (TH) levels, reflecting confidence in species hypotheses based on genetic clustering, expert validation, and linkage to type material.
- BOLD Systems uses the Barcode Index Number (BIN) system, which clusters sequences algorithmically; formal taxonomic names are applied only when supported by voucher specimens and/or expert validation.
- PR2 and SILVA flag entries with taxonomic reliability indicators (e.g., validated, inferred, environmental-only).

Ranking systems may rely on different types of evidence, including:

- Presence of a verified voucher specimen or living culture;
- Linkage to a peer-reviewed publication or recognized taxonomic authority;
- Geographical and ecological consistency (biogeographical plausibility);
- Sequence quality metrics (e.g., absence of stop codons, chimera screening, alignment coherence);
- Representation of multiple sequences for a given taxon to capture intraspecific genetic diversity

Some libraries compute a quantitative composite score integrating multiple criteria, such as:

- Sequence quality (e.g., completeness, error screening);
- Phylogenetic congruence (alignment and tree-based validation);
- Metadata completeness;
- Expert curation status.

Conceptually, such systems may be expressed as: Confidence = f (Sequence Quality × Taxonomic Validation × Metadata Completeness)

These quantitative scores are often translated into categorical levels, for example:

- A – Verified by expert and linked to type material

- B – High-quality match to curated cluster
- C – Putative identification requiring further review

To promote harmonization across reference libraries, we recommend adopting a minimum, transparent ranking scheme grounded primarily in taxonomic traceability and morphological verification in Figure 4 and detailed here:

Level 1 – Sequence derived from type specimen or type strain.

Level 2 – Sequence from a non-type specimen/strain collected near the type locality, with published morphological information sufficient to unambiguously assign the sample to the taxon.

Level 3 – Sequence from a non-type specimen/strain collected distant from the type locality, with published morphological information sufficient to clearly assign the sample to the taxon.

Level 4 – Sequence from a non-type specimen/strain with published morphological information, but insufficient to unambiguously confirm taxonomic assignment.

Level 5 – Sequence from a non-type strain lacking published morphological documentation.

This framework prioritizes traceability to type material and the availability of diagnostic morphological evidence, while remaining simple enough to implement across diverse taxonomic groups. Additional quality layers (e.g., sequence integrity, phylogenetic congruence, metadata completeness) may be applied as complementary criteria within each level.

Figure 4. A minimum, transparent ranking scheme for reference libraries grounded primarily in taxonomic traceability and morphological verification

4.5 Example of bioinformatics pipelines assisting in reference library curation and sequence quality ranking

Bioinformatic pipelines have been developed to assist experts in curating reference libraries and grading the quality of sequences. Examples of these are:

1- **dbDNA**, available at: <https://github.com/TillMacher/dbDNA>

dbDNA is a two step system. The first step uses the SeqRanker pipeline to set up a curated reference library of taxonomically annotated reference sequences on the principle of species monophyly and expert

specimen verification, as well as sequence quality and length and information such as geography, image, and biological life stage. Compliance with these criteria enable definition of a quality criteria score (gold, silver, bronze, or unreliable). Reference libraries are versioned which enables traceability of downstream assignments. The second step of dbDNA is dedicated to newly generated sequences within routine biomonitoring or ecological studies, which are compared to the previously generated reference library: this assignment pipeline adds a quality score based on the quality score given to the reference sequences in the first step. This pipeline (in particular its first step) aligns with the reference library curation steps recommended here (sequence quality curation, taxonomic curation, quality ranking system).

2- The Barcode Audit and Grade System (BAGS, Fontes et al., 2021) available at : <https://github.com/tadeu95/BAGs> and <https://bags.lsd.di.uminho.pt/>

BAGS provides a simple and rapid means to review large animal DNA barcode datasets available in BOLD through comparison of assigned species names with BIN clusters. A five-grade annotation system breaks down the dataset into different categories, separating and highlighting discordant and problematic records (grade E). Pilot assessment of different animal datasets (fish, crustaceans and insects) indicated the existence of a large proportion of discordant or ambiguous records. However, a closer review of these records showed that most problematic cases were constituted by more or less evident faults that could be straightforwardly clarified (Fontes et al., 2021). Hence, most instances of ambiguity are likely amenable to screening by future automated bioinformatic systems, leaving only a minor proportion of complex cases for human-based resolution.

Recently, Biodiversity Genomics Europe (<https://biodiversitygenomics.eu>) developed a library curation tool consisting of an automated pipeline to focus expert intervention on the resolution of ambiguities in taxonomic assignment of BOLD animal datasets (https://github.com/bge-barcoding/BGE_library_curation_tool). This new system adopted BAGS grades and refined and expanded them to include a ranking for metadata, OTU clustering, representative selection (country, species, OTU) and a curation package with family level phylogenies, among others.

Despite these developments in automated curation systems, their reliance on human revision is still considerable. The recent generalization and public accessibility of Artificial intelligence (AI) systems have clearly shown its extraordinary capabilities to quickly process vast amounts of data and to replicate (or even refine) tasks so far typically performed by humans. The potential for assisting curation of reference libraries is therefore immense. At least one pilot study explored the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and the gradient boosting algorithm XGboost (Chen & Guestrin. 2016) to curate BOLD animal reference libraries, based on the revision of BAGS grade E records using specimen and BIN-associated metadata (Fontes et al., 2024; pers. comm.). The ANN system achieved an accuracy of 91.5% for labelling records as supported or inconclusive, while XGBoost reached 91.2% on the same test datasets, thereby showing great potential in this context. However, for tabular data such as BOLD-derived metadata and extracted features, XGBoost may represent a more practical choice, as it is typically faster to train, less computationally demanding, and offers greater interpretability than deep learning approaches, which are often treated as "black boxes".

5. Interoperability

Wilkinson et al. (2016) define interoperability as “the ability of data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort”, and outline guiding principles describing what is needed to be interoperable (Box 2). Aligning (meta)data to these principles makes it easier for machines and humans to interpret and integrate data from multiple sources. To realise the interoperable network of reference libraries (as outlined in the introduction), we propose principles for interoperability at two levels. Firstly, at the level of each individual library, ensuring interoperable and machine-readable metadata fields. Secondly, at the level of the network landscape, with a data architecture that allows for connectivity between reference libraries and findability/access for the end-user. The goal is to work towards a network of genetic reference libraries that will allow the community to benefit from the plethora of niche and overlapping repositories throughout Europe and ideally globally.

Box 2: The FAIR guiding principles for interoperability¹

I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

The main goal of this principle is to provide a “common understanding” of digital objects by using a standardised knowledge representation language. This language allows us to consistently describe and interpret objects across different systems.

Examples: `RDF` `OWL` `JSON-LD`

I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

When we are describing data or metadata, we often use vocabularies that provide the terms or concepts that are adequate to represent their content. However, if we use vocabulary in our data or metadata, we should make sure that they are also FAIR in their own right so that others, humans or machines, can find, access, interoperate and reuse them.

Examples: `DwC` `MiXs`

I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is a regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, All datasets need to be properly cited (i.e., including their globally unique and persistent identifiers.)

Examples: `WoRMS taxonID` `NCBI sequence accession number`

¹ adapted from <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

5.1. At the sequence record and library levels

In this section, we discuss how to make metadata and curation recommendations applicable to achieve interoperable reference libraries. The interoperability at the library level requires that the proposed metadata follows existing standards and contains machine readable fields. Critically, it is required to have all the metadata fields that are essential for interoperability both at the record level and library level.

5.1.1. Interoperable metadata standards for records

The checklist above (Section 3 - Proposal for a set of essential metadata) lists the metadata considered essential to be provided alongside reference sequences in a reference library. For this information to be interoperable across the landscape, these metadata fields need to be aligned with existing metadata standards.

A metadata standard consists of a set of fields (called terms) describing the metadata, which have fixed names, a clear definition and a fixed vocabulary or pattern to complete their information. This fixed vocabulary ensures that responses to the fields are unambiguous to humans as well as to machines (see Box 3: Machine readable fields and formats).

Three standards are relevant to consider for reference sequences used for biodiversity information:

- The **Genomics Standards Consortium** (GSC, Field 2014) issues and updates the standard of **Minimum Information of any Sequence (MIxS)**. Under the MIxS umbrella, the Minimum Information about a MARker gene Sequence (MIMARKS) and its sub-checklists MIMARKS-specimen (cultured or voucher-identifiable specimens) and MIMARKS-survey (for environmental sources) describe the metadata often relevant to maker based studies. Furthermore these can be combined with an environment specific checklists, e.g. at the ENA, GSC MIxS water as many fields relevant to both marine and freshwater. GSC MIxS is used by INSDC (ENA, NCBI, DDBJ) particularly for sample level metadata such as collection date, longitude and latitude, and environment.
- The **Biodiversity Information Standards group (TDWG)** issues the **Darwin Core (DwC)** standard which provides fields to describe organisms and the biodiversity of taxa. The DwC DNA-derived extension was additionally created to describe metadata fields specific to DNA-based biodiversity data and borrows a lot of terms from the MIxS standard, with some additional terms (Henrik Nilsson et al. 2022, Abarenkov et al. 2023). Although not an official standard, it is currently in use by large biodiversity aggregators such as the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) and Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and their affiliated databases. After the end of its public review in January 2026, the DwC Maintenance Group will issue a new format, the DwC Data Package, which will include a few additional fields.
- The Barcode of Life Data (BOLD) system and UNITE use the **Barcode Core Data Model (BCDM)**. The BCDM is not actually a standard, but because of the sheer amount of important reference data in BOLD, knowledge of this and how it maps to MIxS and DwC is essential (see eDNAquaPlan D3.2 for more detail, including these mappings).

For two or more (meta)data standards to be truly interoperable, an alignment model needs to exist between them that maps the fields of one onto the other, allowing for straightforward conversion of one standard into the other depending on the data system in use. As metadata standards get updated, the alignment models between them should also be updated. Meyer et al. (2023) developed an alignment model mapping DwC Version 2021-03-29 DNA derived extension to MIxS Version 5, after which Task 3.3 “Infrastructure/services, linking and compatibility“ of the eDNAqua-Plan project is developing an updated version based on the latest DwC v1 2023-09-18 and MIxS v6.2. BOLD fields have been mapped to MIxS v6.2 and DwC by the BGE project (<https://github.com/bge-barcoding/StayingMapped/tree/main>).

Such alignments are hierarchical in nature, and field names can consist of a combination of multiple fields with different granularities. Alignments must thus also include a vocabulary alignment.

For each of the metadata fields in our proposed checklist, we propose which standardised term should be used to format and fill in the metadata (Table 3, Table 4). These tables are not finalised, but provide a basis and example framework to further develop after finalisation of the shortlist of essential metadata fields. By aligning ourselves with existing standards, this speeds up adoptions, allows the community to leverage previous data and increases the future sustainability. Here, most terms are taken from GSC's MIxS standard. E.g. the unique identifier describing the original sample, specimen or source material should be informed with the MIxS term `source_mat_id` (<https://w3id.org/mixs/0000026>). A select number of fields were subdivided in multiple fields to represent the granularity of the requested information. E.g. the geographic origin is subdivided into a latitudinal and longitudinal coordinates term (`lat_lon`; <https://w3id.org/mixs/0000009>) and broader geographic location name (`geo_loc_name`; <https://w3id.org/mixs/0000010>).

Where possible values should be from widely used and maintained ontologies such as [ENVO](#) (The Environment Ontology) and [OBI](#) (Ontology for Biomedical Investigations), as these provide built-in interoperability features e.g. handling different granularities and sometimes existing mappings to other ontologies or controlled vocabularies.

Finally, we included metadata fields we believe are essential for interoperability. E.g. for taxonomic assignment, to get all the lineage info of a species, ideally the reference sequence has a taxonID which links to a recognised taxonomy database like the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), NCBI Taxonomy or Catalogue of Life (CoL) and allows human and machine users to reliably retrieve all the desired taxonomic levels.

5.1.2. Interoperable metadata about the reference library

In addition to making sure the proposed record level metadata fields are interoperable, it is important to also include metadata describing the library in itself to ensure that the library is findable and easy to interpret. These are the metadata concepts which would be useful for machines and scientists to decide which reference libraries to use.

5.1.3. Interoperable and accessible databases and file formats

The metadata must be stored in digital and open-access databases or in a publicly accessible database of the storing institution. It is important that the metadata is stored in non-proprietary formats (e.g. text documents in .txt, images in .tif) and that such databases comply with FAIR Data principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and Biodiversity Information Standards, such as the Darwin Core, Audubon Core, or ABCD 2005 standard (<https://www.tdwg.org>). JSON-LD has emerged as a solid format to store metadata (see Box 3).

Together, these metadata ensure traceability, taxonomic accuracy, and interoperability across projects and databases. They enable consistent reuse of curated sequences for eDNA metabarcoding, phylogenetics, and biodiversity monitoring, providing the foundation for robust, reproducible ecological inference.

Box 3: Machine-readable fields and formats

Machine-readable needs the interoperable standards and ideally the removal of nuances and ambiguities that an experienced scientist can take in their stride. Machine-readable means that the (meta)data is provided in a defined, well structured format that can be readily interpreted.

Machine-readable fields: In the GSC MlxS standard, there is a field_name called **target_gene** and it has a corresponding Currie formatted identifier MIXS:0000044, if you use these then scientists would know what it is, however this is still hard for machines. **Uniform Resource Identifiers(URI)** were developed to solve this problem e.g. <https://w3id.org/mixs/0000044>. These also have other desirable qualities such as being persistent (a type of PURL) and allow current and future scientists to follow the link and discover more detail, such as description.

Machine-readable formats: Spreadsheets, TSV and CSV files can be well structured, but are hard for machines to unambiguously decode. **JSON** is an [increasingly recommended format](#), particularly [JSON-LD\(JSON-based format to serialize Linked Data\)](#) and [JSON Schema](#). **XML** works fairly well too, although is more often found in older systems. Other formats are used too, such as [Linked Open Data](#)

Key advantages of both XML and JSON are that they are computer language independent, extensible(can easily add new fields) and define the embedded data types e.g. arrays or name-value pairs. Neither formats are panaceas and care needs to be taken to ensure the (meta)data will be interoperable. Many APIs (Application programming interfaces) allow a choice of exports in JSON and TSV/CSV, which allows users to get what is appropriate for them e.g. JSON for most machines and tabular data for scientists who prefer that.

Table 3. Interoperable terms for each of the mandatory (bold) and recommended essential metadata fields at the record level.

Field name	Description	Standard term	Term source	Term definition
BIOLOGICAL ORIGIN				
Source sample identifier	unique specimen/sample/strain code.	source_mat_id	https://w3id.org/mixs/0000026	A unique identifier assigned to a material sample (as defined by http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/materialSampleID , and as opposed to a particular digital record of a material sample) used for extracting nucleic acids, and subsequent sequencing. The identifier can refer either to the original material collected or to any derived sub-samples.
Repository	name of museum, biobank, culture collection from which specimen originates.	repository_name	https://w3id.org/mixs/0001152	The name of the institution where the sample or DNA extract is held or "sample not available" if the sample was used in its entirety for analysis or otherwise not retained
Sample type	whether the barcode originates from an individual specimen, a culture, or an environmental sequencing dataset.	samp_type	https://w3id.org/mixs/0000998	The type of material from which the sample was obtained. For the Hydrocarbon package, samples include types like core, rock trimmings, drill cuttings, piping section, coupon, pigging debris, solid deposit, produced fluid, produced water, injected water, swabs, etc. For the Food Package, samples are usually categorized as food, body products or tissues, or environmental material. This field accepts terms listed under environmental specimen (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/GENEPIO_0001246)

Field name	Description	Standard term	Term source	Term definition
Date of collection	preferably in ISO-format (YYYY-MM-DD).	collection_date	https://w3id.org/mixs/0000011	The time of sampling, either as an instance (single point in time) or interval. In case no exact time is available, the date/time can be right truncated i.e. all of these are valid times: 2008-01-23T19:23:10+00:00; 2008-01-23T19:23:10; 2008-01-23; 2008-01; 2008; Except: 2008-01; 2008 all are ISO8601 compliant
Geographic coordinates	Latitude/longitude (expressed in decimal values in WGS84 format or in a different, specified geographical position system).	lat_lon	https://w3id.org/mixs/0000009	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by latitude and longitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees, limited to 8 decimal points, and in WGS84 system
Country	Country name	geo_loc_name	https://w3id.org/mixs/0000009	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by the country or sea name followed by specific region name. Country or sea names should be chosen from the INSDC country list (http://insdc.org/country.html), or the GAZ ontology (http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/GAZ)
Source sample identification	taxonomic name linked to specimen by person who originally identified it	scientificName	http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/scientificNameID	An identifier for the nomenclatural (not taxonomic) details of a scientific name.
SEQUENCE INFORMATION				
Sequence accession number	Accession number assigned by sequence repository.	accession number	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/GENEPIO_0100605	A unique identifier given to a sequence record to allow for tracking of different versions of that sequence record and the associated sequence over time in a single data repository
Source database name	Database hosting the sequence (ENA, GenBank, BOLD, PR2, etc.).		https://schema.org/name	The name of the item.
Source database version	Version or release of the database where the sequence is deposited.		https://schema.org/version	The version of the CreativeWork embodied by a specified resource.
Marker / gene	Genetic marker sequenced (e.g., 18S, COI, rbcL, ITS). This can be controlled vocabulary.	target_gene	https://w3id.org/mixs/0000044	Targeted gene or locus name for marker gene studies
Marker / gene region	e.g., 18S v4, COI, rbcL, ITS. This can be more variable.	target_subfragment	https://w3id.org/mixs/0000045	Name of subfragment of a gene or locus. Important to e.g. identify special regions on marker genes like V6 on 16S rRNA
Sequencing platform	Sequencing platform (e.g. Sanger, Illumina, Nanopore)	sequencing platform (brand)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/GENEPIO_0000071	A sequencing platform (brand) is a name of a company that produces sequencer equipment.
Sequencing instrument	Sequencing instrument	sequencing instrument	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0400103	A DNA sequencer is an instrument that determines the order of deoxynucleotides in deoxyribonucleic acid sequences.
Sequence length	Length of the sequence in base pairs.			
Quality metrics	Quality metrics (e.g., % ambiguous bases, Phred score - defined list?)			

Field name	Description	Standard term	Term source	Term definition
Quality control notes	Quality control notes (e.g., chimera check, contamination screening, trimming notes)	seq_quality_check	https://w3id.org/mixs/0000051	Indicate if the sequence has been called by automatic systems (none) or undergone a manual editing procedure (e.g. by inspecting the raw data or chromatograms).
TAXONOMY AND TAXONOMIC VALIDATION				
Curation status	Data status (raw, expert-reviewed).	assertion method	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ECO_0000217	A means by which a statement is made about an entity.
Curator / validator	Expert reviewer name (and optional institution/contact).	identifiedByID	http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/identifiedByID	A list (concatenated and separated) of the globally unique identifier for the person, people, groups, or organizations responsible for assigning the dwc:Taxon to the subject.
Confidence level score/rank	The confidence level of the taxonomic identification			
Scientific name	The current valid name according to an accepted taxonomy - the most reliable identification to the lowest possible taxonomic rank.	scientificName	http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/scientificName	The full scientific name, with authorship and date information if known. When forming part of a dwc:Identification, this should be the name in lowest level taxonomic rank that can be determined.
Taxonomic identifier	Identifier corresponding to the scientific name (e.g., NCBI TaxID, WORMS AlphaID).	identificationID	http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/identificationID	An identifier for the dwc:Identification (the body of information associated with the assignment of a scientific name). May be a global unique identifier or an identifier specific to the data set.
Taxonomic source	name of taxonomic database (e.g., WoRMS, AlgaeBase, NCBI Taxonomy, SILVA).			
Taxonomic rank	Lowest rank assigned (species, genus, family, etc.).	taxonRank	http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/taxonRank	The taxonomic rank of the most specific name in the dwc:scientificName.

Table 4. Interoperable terms for each of the mandatory (bold) and recommended essential metadata fields at the library level.

Field name	Description	Standard term	Term source	Term definition
LIBRARY METADATA				
Library name	The name of the reference library		https://schema.org/name	The name of the item.
Library version number	Version of the current reference library release, ideally using semantic versioning.		https://schema.org/version	The version of the CreativeWork embodied by a specified resource.
Library version date	release date of the version in YYYY-MM-DD (ISO 8061)		https://schema.org/datePublished	Date of first publication or broadcast. For example the date a CreativeWork was broadcast or a Certification was issued.
Library marker region coverage	List of marker genes that this reference library (ideally controlled vocabulary)		https://schema.org/Gene	A discrete unit of inheritance which affects one or more biological traits (Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gene). Examples include FOXP2 (Forkhead box protein P2), SCARNA21 (small Cajal body-specific RNA 21), A- (agouti genotype).
Library geographic coverage	The continent, countries or seas which this library is focused on.	spatialCoverage	https://schema.org/spatialCoverage	The spatialCoverage of a CreativeWork indicates the place(s) which are the focus of the content. It is a subproperty of contentLocation intended primarily for more technical and detailed materials. For example with a Dataset, it indicates areas that the dataset describes: a dataset of New York weather would have spatialCoverage which was the place: the state of New York.
Library taxonomic coverage	The main taxonomic groups targeted in this reference library	taxonomicRange	https://schema.org/taxonomicRange	The taxonomic grouping of the organism that expresses, encodes, or in some way related to the BioChemEntity.
Library taxonomic system	The taxonomic backbone used in this reference library			
Library publication	a/several paper(s) describing the library	bibliographicCitation	http://purl.org/dc/terms/bibliographicCitation	A bibliographic reference for the resource.
Library link	A URL hyperlink to the reference library site		https://schema.org/url	URL of the item.
Library total records	The number of records present in this library		https://schema.org/amountOfThisGood	The quantity of the goods included in the offer.

5.2. At the landscape level: Data architecture

There are different possibilities to make the federated system happen, in a sustainable and pragmatic fashion. This is a journey, by agreeing and exchanging standard formats of minimal metadata and data by file, that can be a stepping stone to fuller metadata and even by API for purer data federation. Below we detail and discuss two solutions that we consider most achievable in the short to medium term and are illustrated in figure 5.

Figure 5. Several data architectures are possible for federation, where all the reference libraries either 1) have standardised APIs or 1) periodically exchange their latest data in standardised format.

5.2.1. Maintain reference libraries individually managed and on separate servers.

Each reference library will need to have their own portal and API etc. and will need to provide this API conforming to agreed consistency in this federate, distributed system. Each portal will then in turn be able to query across other portal's APIs. In this from any single portal you have queryable access to any other reference library.

Advantages: Simplicity for the user and politically all portals are equal. In theory if one server is down, you can still access all but that server's reference libraries,

Disadvantages: How do connections get established? Apparently, this is difficult. It can be very intensive to build a webcrawler to access all of them separately with each search and also some servers may sometimes be out of action. Most of these reference libraries are poorly funded and lack a dedicated IT person, yet alone a multi-skilled IT team to keep them maintained.

5.2.2. Maintain reference libraries individually managed but periodically export to a central server

Each reference library portal is individually managed with releasing data exports / data dumps in an agreed-upon format. These need to follow the proposed metadata and data standard. A central repository centralises the versioned copies of separate databases in one location.

As a variant could provide versioned data dumps of individual repositories in the agreed formats to GitHub or Zenodo. A value add would be to provide changes between releases in individual repositories in a structured form e.g. in LDES standard.

Advantages: This adds redundancy, but also makes the indexing and access easier/feasible as it is asynchronous. A central search portal can then be built on this repository. The copies are still linked to the original databases, owned by them, and correctly cited at each re-use. The separate databases maintain their independence whilst making their data more easily accessible and interoperable..

N.B. This is currently a similar data pattern to how GBIF works.

Disadvantages: There is a single point of failure with the central repository and portal. A regular data export from all reference library resources actually needs to happen and regularly.

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